
EFFECT OF THE GET-RICH QUICK SYNDROME ON THE ASPIRATIONS OF SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS: THE NIGERIA EXPERIENCE

Ngozi Ezema-Kalu (Ph.D)
Department of Education Foundations
Faculty of Education
08033362108
ngozikalu88@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Nigeria has witnessed remarkable and swift change as a result of the influence of the internet where a large proportion of it has led to increased cybercrime and distortion of our value system. In recent time, there is increasing rate of youths' engagement in cybercrime, of which the notorious yahoo-yahoo is paramount in the country. This study therefore investigates the effect of get-rich quick syndrome on the aspirations of secondary school students: The Nigerian experience. The study posed three research questions, and adopted cross-sectional through a quantitative method, whereby 200 secondary schools students selected from Port Harcourt were shared copies of questionnaire to fill and submit. 164 copies of questionnaire were retrieved and used for the analysis. Snowballing sampling technique was employed in gathering the sample elements. The instruments for data collection in this study were a self-designed structured questionnaire. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions. The findings of this study revealed a significant impact on research question one, that is, the responses on "the activities of get-rich quick syndrome on the aspirations of secondary school students in Nigeria". Also, mean score and standard deviation scores signify that the statement items on the implications of students' involvement in cybercrime on the educational sector of Nigeria were all agreed by the participants. The study further found that, a significant impact exists on the causes of get-rich quick syndrome among secondary school students in Nigeria. The study therefore concludes that get-rich quick syndrome affects the aspirations of secondary schools students. The study recommends that because of the high rate of incessancy of this crime in the country there is immediate call for remedies. An important solution is for government to address the poor living condition of youths, as well as the high rate of poverty and unemployment facing youths in the country.

Keywords: Get-Rich Quick Syndrome, Secondary School, Cybercrime

1.0 INTRODUCTION

The invention of the internet technology marked a remarkable turn-around in the life of citizens of nations. The Internet has facilitated global business and social interactions. It has indeed turned the world to a global village. It has greatly contributed in enhancing communication and interaction between people irrespective of their location in the globe. Nigeria has witnessed tremendous and rapid change through social media where large proportion not only in corrupting the Nigerian value system, but constitutes a big threat to people's financial and privacy security (Nwokoro et al., 2022). Unfortunately, rather than work to acquire wealth and live the kind of life they desire, most Nigerian youths crave for get-rich-quick schemes (Ogunrin, 2018). It is clearly possible to get rich quickly if one is prepared to accept very high levels of risk. The foundation of the gambling sector is this. Even though gambling occasionally results in victories along the way, the long-term odds of losing the entire initial investment are almost inevitable. Get-rich-quick advocates held the belief that generating income while working from home is possible.

Get-rich-quick scams that are both legal and illegal are widely promoted in periodicals, newspapers, and infomercials. Spam or cold calling is frequently used to market illegal schemes or frauds. Some of the adverts for these schemes promote books or CDs about how to get rich quickly rather than urging viewers to put money into a specific program. The rate at which secondary school students indulge in get-rich-quick schemes is alarming. Recently in Delta State, an SS1 student bought a Mercedes Benz car and brought it to school, his fellow students were seen cheering him up. This has sent a signal to other fellow students to look for quick money. Ndubueze et al. (2023) in Lagos discovered that many young people in Nigeria spend the entire day online due to the high prevalence of unemployment as well as the perception that they may get rich rapidly online. The over-emphasis on wealth by the Nigerian society has left the youth with no other choice but to pursue it, albeit by hook or crook. Ogunrin (2018) reported that 80% of cybercrime perpetrators were students in higher educational institutions. Ojekodum and Eraye (2022) argued that most Yahoo boys are between the age of 16 and 30, and that they are either enrolled in a secondary school, university or about to be admitted to the university.

This get-rich-quick syndrome has become a social sickness that has eaten deep into the fabric of our schools. The typical Nigeria youth already longs for personal jets, limos, and homes with renowned architectural designs, among other things. Ask him what he intends to do to justify his dreams, he has no logical answer. An inordinate craze for wealth has given Nigeria ignoble names among the comity of nations. This is because of the value which the present generation of youths in Nigeria seem to attach to a "Get-Rich-Quick," mindset through cybercrime, gambling, selling of own body organs, kidnapping and the use of human blood or body parts for money ritual. This can be corroborated by the present poverty situation that clearly manifests with the denial of opportunities, unemployment and inequality in wealth distribution. The average Nigerian is a poor person. Nigeria is a rich country but majority of its inhabitants are poor because of inequality in wealth distribution (World Bank, 2020). This inequality in wealth distribution, unemployment especially among youths and corruption especially among politicians and public office holders, has increased the rate of poverty (Ucha, 2020). There are several effects associated with poverty in Nigeria. Some of such effects are high crime rates like cyber fraud, kidnapping, prostitution and motivated ritual killings for moneymaking by the present generation of Nigerian youths.

Eze-Michael (2021) observes that some Internet fraudsters use internet dating to obtain money from their victims when they pretend to be in search of a life partner. Kamruzzaman

et al., (2020) in a study, found that male students are more likely to engage in get-rich-quick schemes than females and that most of the respondents who are involved in them do so just for the mere interest and not for the illegal monetary gain. Males are more prone than girls to engage in harmful online leisure activities like accessing unknown websites, downloading free games, free music, and free movies, according to a 2023 study by Choi et al. in Japan. Also, Elgbadon and Adejuwon (2017) in Asuai & Ebebuwa-Okoh (2023) in a study in Lagos and Ibadan aimed at finding out factors that predict engagement in get-rich-quick schemes among young using 986 young people found that males are more likely to engage in internet fraud than females. According to Odo and Odo (2020), the large number of people involved in cybercrimes and other social media crime fall within the age bracket of 18 to 30 years of age. It is from this premise that this study is undertaken to examine the effect of the get-rich quick syndrome on the aspirations of secondary school students: The Nigerian experience.

1.1 OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The aim of this study is to empirically investigate the effect of get-rich quick syndrome on the aspirations of secondary school students: The Nigerian experience. The specific objectives are to:

- i. Determine the activities of get-rich quick syndrome on the aspirations of secondary school students in Nigeria.
- ii. Examine the implications of secondary school students' involvement in cybercrime on the educational sector of Nigeria.
- iii. To discuss the causes of get-rich quick syndrome among secondary school students in Nigeria.

1.2. RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The following research questions were raised to guide the study:

- i. What are the activities of get-rich quick syndrome on the aspirations of secondary school students in Nigeria?
- ii. What are the implications of students' involvement in cybercrime on the educational sector of Nigeria?
- iii. What are the causes of get-rich quick syndrome among secondary school students in Nigeria?

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

Concept of Get-Rich Quick Syndrome

Get-rich quick syndrome held the belief that generating income while working from home is possible. Get-rich-quick scams that are both legal and illegal are widely promoted in periodicals, newspapers, and infomercials. Individuals are involve in many things to get rich quick, like gambling, Ponzi scheme, cybercrime, selling of own body vital organs, ritualism, selling of body parts, kidnapping, prostitution and other social vices. Due to this circumstance, crimes like murder, kidnapping, and robbery have increased, and today the principal occupation of most youth is the pursuit of material prosperity. As a result, many of them are now drug dealers. They now specialize in defrauding people through fake pretences to accumulate wealth. This has led to a falling standard of education as most students now have a lukewarm attitude to academics but a quick way to become a millionaire (Akah & Uzoh, 2019). So many factors may be responsible for get-rich-quick syndrome among

students in Nigeria. These boys are seen in major cities in Nigeria, driving through popular streets in convoys and sometimes deliberately obstructing traffic flow with the mind of attracting attention of the public to their immoral display. Sometimes they consciously abandon their exotic cars on the middle of the roads just to throw or spray money and each time they do, people usually gather to watch their unholy and inglorious display of stolen money.

It appears that the society has become helpless and rather than resist this ugly trend, is unwittingly supporting the activities and atrocities of these criminal gangs (Chukwuka, 2022). The most worrisome aspect of yahoo business is the spiritual dimension the illicit business has taken. The yahoo boys, especially the G-Boys, are heavily involved in human rituals and sacrifice (Ogwezzy, 2021). According to Onodarho (2021), a recent phenomenon in the operation of Yahoo boys is the inter-mix of spiritual elements with cybercrimes. There are spiritualists, witchdoctors and sorcerers who work hand in hand with them. For the effectiveness of the illicit business, human parts such as sexual organs, tongue, breast, etc are used to prepare toxic charm for yahoo practitioners. These spiritual lords initiate and prepare magic wands for them with which they are able to lure their target into accepting their business proposals. In return they are made to sacrifice either a human life or a part of their vital organs in lieu of sacrificing a loved one. The purpose of this sacrifice is to renew the magic wand and making it continuously efficacious. Another reason for the sacrifice is to maintain their membership of the wicked gangs. As a result of the above, members of the families of yahoo persons are in danger of being mysteriously killed by their sons or brothers for sacrifice. They are usually commanded to make sacrifice of a family member that is so dear to them. It could also be their girlfriend or any friend. They do this to secure their wealth. The yahoo boys who fail to make sacrifices when demanded are usually in danger.

Youths that choose to go for get-rich quick use several methods to capture their prey especially those in cybercrime. They usually target international business and in particular, foreign merchants who are seeking for international on-line business. Their methods include phishing but others call it spoofing. This method involves scamming of the victim. This is done by sending messages using e-mail where the fraudster pretends to have a legitimate business in an attempt to deceive his target thereby the recipient begins to voluntarily give out vital information about him and the business such as passwords, credit card number and bank account details. A fake website is usually opened in order to obtain those vital information that will enable them defraud their victims (Obiezu, 2021). Another method employed by the yahoo boys is Automatic Teller Machine (ATM) fraud. The boys who use this method in defrauding members of the public usually hang around the ATM of different banks, pretending to be staffs on duty ready to help any customer who may have difficulty in operating the machines. These boys take advantage of Nigerians in this category and in the process of assisting gains access to vital information which they use in swapping cards (Eze-Michael, 2021).

Activities of Get-Rich Quick Syndrome

A. Cybercrime (Yahoo Yahoo)

Cybercrime in Nigeria is largely perpetrated by young people and students in secondary and tertiary institutions, and are socially tagged yahoo yahoo or yahoo boys. A major problem in the study of cyber-crime is the absence of a consistent current definition, even among those law enforcement agencies charged with tackling it. To the Council of Europe (COE) Convention on Cyber-crime, cyber-crime involves “action directed against the confidentiality, integrity and availability of computer systems, networks and computer data as

well as the misuse of such systems, networks and data” (Regner et al., 2022). Yahoo boys rely on their computer dexterity to victimize unsuspecting persons in cyberspace. A new phenomenon in cybercrime is mixing spiritual elements with internet surfing to boost cybercrime success rates. The rising popularity of cybercrime may not be unconnected to the fact that the Nigerian state is currently experiencing economic imbalance with attendant high rate of unemployment among able-bodied youths, erosion of traditional values of integrity, and quick-money syndrome. The Economic and Financial Crimes Commission (EFCC) has recorded several arrests and prosecution of cyber-crime suspects. Examples of such include the arrest of six “yahoo boys” in Abuja; prosecution of an arrested suspect who attempted to bribe EFCC operatives with 28.7 million Naira (19,140 US dollars), and several other apprehensions and prosecutions in the last one year (EFCC, 2023). Cyber-crimes target laptops, tablets, mobile phones and entire networks. Mobile merchants are reported to be incurring the greatest fraud losses as a percentage of revenue amongst all merchant segments (Melvin & Ayotunde, 2020).

In Nigeria, “yahoo yahoo” refers to the activities which entail the use of computers, phones and the Internet to defraud unsuspecting victims, especially those outside the country. The term “yahoo yahoo” originated from the fact that the use of Yahoo e-mails and Yahoo instant messenger was a dominant medium of communication between perpetrators and victims (Okogba, 2018). Those who are involved in “yahoo yahoo” are popularly referred to as “yahoo boys”. With the popularity of Gmail services and use, “yahoo boys” are now being referred to as G boys. With the spread of awareness of “yahoo yahoo” and sensitization of potential victims, a group of “yahoo boys” have resorted to the inclusion of magic and spiritual powers to aid the defrauding of victims (Melvin & Ayotunde, 2020). This phenomenon is referred to as yahoo plus, and perpetrators are referred to as “yahoo boys” plus. It encompasses all illegal activities perpetrated by one or more people referred to as scammers, hackers, internet fraudsters, cyber citizens or 419ners, using the internet through the medium of networked computers, telephones and other information and communications technology (ICT) equipment.

Various Channels of Cyber Crime

The popularity of cybercrime has led to its openness in most social media and internet social platforms. Some of the known channels of cybercrime include:

a. Free Tickets/Vouchers Scams: This cybercrime comes as gift cards to popular stores or restaurants. They are advertised in emails as ads on websites or shared in some social media handle. Once someone fall victim and click on these freebies’ links, he/she can be scammed and the perpetrators usually harvest secret information related to bank accounts or assets.

b. Crypto Currency Scams: According to Button and Cross (2023), in this type of cybercrime, victims will be invited to sign up to crypto currencies in social media or so-called investment sites and once the person falls victim to this scam, their personal information will be retrieved and used for further hacking. In some cases, victims realize only after the website has been deactivated and suspects can no longer be contacted, that they have been defrauded.

c. Personal Data Fraudsters: Personal data fraudsters usually persuade victims to send their personal data for a promo or other scams. Once retrieved, the perpetrators will clone the identity of the victim and use it for their benefits. This is usually carried out in most social media outlets (Button & Cross, 2023).

d. Free Trial Products: Social media sites are often used to lure people into signing up for free trials on products. These scams usually involve the participant signing up for a free trial of a product which is often not genuine instructing them to provide their payment card details upfront (Tade, 2023). The victims then become tied into a fixed period contract unbeknownst to them and have provided their payment card details to an unknown individual.

e. Investment Scams: In this type of cybercrime, opportunities are advertised on social media sites for people to invest in products or businesses which are often fake or do not exist. Fraudsters advertise a ‘too good to be true’ investment opportunity, sometimes using news stories and advertisements that appear to be from genuine sources (Tade, 2023). Consumers who are tempted to invest lose some or all of their money.

f. SOS or Help Messages: This scam involves social media account holders receiving messages from persons in their “friends” or “contacts” list indicating that they are in trouble in a foreign country and need help. This message usually requests that they transfer money to an account in a foreign country. The content of the messages varies but popular ones tell the story that the person has been arrested and needs money for bailing, once someone falls victim to this scam, a huge sum of money is pulled out of their bank account.

g. Fake Friend Requests: In this kind, social media account holders would receive friend requests from people that they do not know or from people already in their contacts who have had their accounts hacked. Accepting these requests causes the account of the victim and that of their friends to be hacked, and their entire personal data accessed.

B. Human Rituals

The most worrisome aspect of yahoo business is the spiritual dimension the illicit business has taken. The yahoo boys, especially the G-Boys, are heavily involved in human rituals and sacrifice (Ogwezzy, 2021). Apart from these youths, many Nigerian elites, including business men and women, politicians, artists, celebrities and socialites also engage in human rituals for money making, fame, power, electoral success and for protection. For example, in Lagos in 2017, the Nigeria Police arrested a member of a gang popularly known as “Badoo Boys”. The suspect confessed that the business men and women, celebrities, socialites, politicians and public office holders pay them as much as one hundred dollars (\$100) for stolen ladies pants, used menstruation pad and five thousand dollars (\$5000) for an handkerchief soaked with human blood of motivated ritual killing for protection, money making, fame and power (Obadare, 2022). The ritual killers perpetrate the evil by killing their victims and collecting their blood or removing vital organs (especially the reproductive sexual organs, eyes, heart, breasts, head, tongue, toes and fingers) from the victim for rituals. Some however prefer to use their own sperm or inflict themselves with occult ulceric sore as a form of indigenous epistemology for acquiring sudden and unimaginable wealth.

The belief is that the invisible metaphysical world of spirits and forces holds the key to wealth, riches, prosperity power and fame and this can only be achieved by using human blood or body parts for the ritual. The belief in the existence, influence and efficacies of the invisible metaphysical world of spirit and forces as a way of making money, riches, prosperity, fame and power only confirms the myths about man’s relationship with the metaphysical and spiritual world. Yet, this traditional African system, rituals and indigenous epistemologies of acquiring sudden and unimaginable wealth and prosperity do, however, not endure for long because evidence has shown that it attracts serious repercussions such as sudden calamities befalling the wealth or sudden ailment or death of the ritual killer. Also,

sometimes, the children of the ritual killer could be spiritually doomed to pay with miserable life, mysterious death or mental illness (Adedayo, 2021).

C. Deceitfulness

The word deceitfulness is from the noun “deceit” which means to deliberately mislead a person. The deceitfulness of riches therefore implies that wrong impression and opinion which riches tend to create in the minds of people. There are indeed many myths built around money and everyone grows up with at least one or more of them. Some of them actually come to us through enculturation by our parents (Templar, 2020). To have money is good and if anyone works hard, he/she stands a better chance of becoming rich. The harder and smarter a person works the more he/ she will earn. However, there are some persons who believe that money is everything as a result they are ready to obtain or acquire it by hook or crook. This group of persons hold that money could be made through means other than working harder, smarter and diligently. As a result they engage in computer crimes, gambling, pool betting, yahoo business, money ritual, kidnapping for money, human trafficking and the likes. Unfortunately, many Nigerian youths are now interested in acquiring huge wealth without any verifiable and legitimate business. They are deceived to think that how one gets his money is not as important as having money. They are ready to stop at nothing until they have made enough money. Similarly, having a wrong impression about riches can result in some social vices such as theft, fraud, murder, etc.

D. Internet Fraud:

The term internet fraud refers to a fraud scheme that uses email, website, chat rooms, or message boards to present fraudulent solicitations to prospective victims, to conduct fraudulent transactions or to transmit the proceeds of fraud to financial institutions or others connected with the scheme (Obiezu, 2021). It is a type of cybercrime or deception which makes use of the internet and could involve the hiding of information or providing incorrect information for the purpose of tricking victims out of money, property, and inheritance. Furthermore, fraud is a wrongful or criminal deception intended to result in financial or personal gain. It is an intentional deception made for personal gain. The specific legal definition of fraud varies by legal jurisdiction. In some jurisdictions, Fraud is a crime, and also a civil law violation. Nigeria has been at the frontline of internet fraud and other cybercrime around the globe. The nation has been marked for its peak involvement in cyber-enabled crimes which is prevalent among the youth. This prevailing attitude has posed threats to the moral, intellectual, legal, and financial development of youths in Nigeria.

Yahoo boys use several methods to capture their prey. They usually target international business and in particular, foreign merchants who are seeking for international on-line business. Their methods include phishing but others call it spoofing. This method involves scamming of the victim. This is done by sending messages using e-mail where the fraudster pretends to have a legitimate business in an attempt to deceive his target thereby the recipient begins to voluntarily give out vital information about him and the business such as passwords, credit card number and bank account details. A fake website is usually opened in order to obtain those vital information that will enable them defraud their victims (Obiezu, 2021). Another method employed by the yahoo boys is Automatic Teller Machine (ATM) fraud. The boys who use this method in defrauding members of the public usually hang around the ATM of different banks, pretending to be staffs on duty ready to help any customer who may have difficulty in operating the machines (Eze-Michael, 2021). One of the commonest and biggest internet fraud carried out by the yahoo boys is on-line shopping

fraud. There are many on-line businesses. Some are genuine while some are not. Fraudsters usually display products and services on their websites. The products are usually attractive but with relatively low price tags which compels some customers to desire to engage in the business. Once money is paid and received, the fraudsters may either close the portal making it impossible for anybody to reach them for complaint or they will supply products that are inferior to the ones paid for (Abiola, 2023).

Another dimension of internet fraud is internet dating and marriage. Some successfully married on the internet while others have ended up losing their lives and or their money. Matrimonial or dating fraud remains one of the methods use by the yahoo boys to steal from members of the international community. Eze-Michael (2021) observes that some Internet fraudsters use internet dating to obtain money from their victims when they pretend to be in search of a life partner. Another common method that the yahoo boys employ in their illicit business is what is called 'identity theft'. This is used to lure victims into a kind of relationship or business with the intention of using that as opportunity to defraud their victims. Yahoo boys may use the name, photograph or forged document of a well known business or personality.

Adverse Effect of Cybercrime on the Nigerian Economy

1. Internet Fraud is a common plague, it can and does affect every country of the world. However, when it is handled poorly, internet fraud can result in an erosion of trust in government and industries, and lead to a loss of international and economic reputation. This is particularly true when the internet fraud is facilitated by corruption and perceived by the global world to be supported by the government. In Nigeria, it is common knowledge that the prevalent fraud in Nigeria is thriving because of the existing corruption in the system already. This has earned us a bad reputation in the global world, thereby reducing foreign investment in Nigeria, which has affected in totality the growth of our economy. More so, the reputational damage affects even individuals in Nigeria, as the global world has no confidence in Nigerians, within and outside the borders of the country.
2. Internet Fraud has resulted in distorted markets. It has created a market system where fraudsters obtain competitive advantage and drive out legitimate businesses. This has affected services delivered by businesses in Nigeria and exposed other sectors to further incidences of fraud.
3. It has undermined national defence and security in Nigeria and this has contributed to negative output in the economy.
4. It has affected our economy negatively because it has damaged our international standing and has affected the ability of our nation to get international support.
5. A lot of funds are lost to internet fraud, some of which are eventually used to fund organised crime groups and terrorism, potentially leading to further crime and terrorist attacks.
6. Loss of online business and consumer confidence in the digital economy.
7. Costs to government agencies and businesses in re-establishing credit histories, accounts and identities. • Costs to businesses in improving cyber security measures. • Stimulating other criminal activity. • Costs in time and resources for law enforcement agencies.

Causes of Get-Rich Quick Syndrome among Secondary School Students in Nigeria

The following are some of the causes of cybercrime in Nigeria:

Peer Pressure: Peer pressure is influence from members of one's peer group or circle. When a typical young man sees his secondary school or university best friend flaunting designer shoes on social media, they are pressured to get rich no matter the means. Several youths want to be like their mates.

Greed: It is that intense and selfish desire for something, in this case, wealth. Several young people simply want the whole world to themselves without proportional effort put in. For many, the fastest way to this is internet fraud, which even in reality is not as easy as it seems.

Disappearance of Cherished Family and Societal Values: Values such as honesty, diligence and trust are already eroded in the known smallest and fundamental social unit called family, thereby, festering and impacting on the larger society. These youths live dishonest life style, see no importance in being diligent and are not trustworthy. There is craving to trade right societal values for wealth. Sadly, parents of these so called yahoo guys see nothing bad in what their children are doing and they even support them with prayers and other diabolical means.

Increasing Indolent Youths: The prominence which internet fraud has gained has regrettably turned sizable number of youths in their productive age into half-baked, unnecessarily lazy and dependent population. Painfully, some of these youths who had one job or productive skill are losing focus on them and deviating ingloriously into this pervasive trend called yahoo yahoo (Faturoti, 2022)

Extravagance Life-style: According to Faturoti (2022), one obvious feature of a yahoo boy is lavish living. They go for expensive items with little or no maintenance knowledge. They ride expensive cars more than their productive efforts can acquire and even drive recklessly, endangering their lives and those of others.

Drugs/Alcohol and Reckless Sexual Life: Proceeds of internet fraud are heavily spent on harmful drugs, hard alcoholic spirits, clubbing and ladies of easy virtues. Hard and expensive drugs are brazenly abused leading to addiction and mental derangement. Alcohols, champagnes, and wines that cost heavily are used and often wasted in the name of celebrations and oppressive tendencies to fellow hustlers and other members of the society to announce their hit or what they call "cash-out" (Faturoti, 2022).

Depression: This is a feeling of severe despondency and dejection often caused by unfortunate circumstances that negatively affect how you feel, the way you think and how you act. It might be subsequent to oppression, which may make a young man thinking deeply about his life, then resort to Yahoo Yahoo internet fraud.

Unproductive Lodging in Hotels: In the spirit of celebration or show, these boys and girls check into expensive hotels for longer durations running into weeks and months when they cash-out. The cost of their prolong stay in these hotels is enough to make most of them for life, if put into profitable ventures. To maintain this lifestyle, there is the push for more fraud and crime.

Acquisition and Use of Smart Devices and Accessories: These boys purchase costly phones and smart devices running into hundreds of thousands. Beside smart mobile devices possession, body accessories such as diamond, gold and silver plated necklaces, chains, ubans, studs, dreadlocks and so on, are common features and identities of yahoo boys.

Impatience: Most young people are in a hurry to get rich; this has led to boycotting of legitimate process of getting wealth by many (Oladoye & Ushie, 2019). They crave for rocket science wealth and the wanting of magical effects in all situations. The inability to calm down and wait for results subsequent to positive actions often lead to wrong reactions, Yahoo Yahoo internet fraud, in this case.

Acute Poverty: This is a very serious shortage of purchasing power or of access to resources that provide the basic necessities of life, such as food and shelter. In cases like this, coupled with some other factors, some are left with no other alternative but to go into the illegal act of cybercrime.

Unemployment and Unfavourable Economy: The rate of unemployment in Nigeria is very high. However, it is the belief of the researcher, the above reasons notwithstanding, none of the highlighted reasons is a justification for yahoo yahoo. This is because there are many people who are in the same society, and are making legitimate wealth without involving in fraudulent acts.

The Implications of Students' Involvement in Cybercrime on the Educational Sector of Nigeria

1. Tarnishing the Country's Education Reputation: Without any doubt, internet fraud has tarnished the image of this country in the international arena to an irreparable level. Cybercrime has created a bad image for Nigeria which has earned her a spot in the present ranking in Transparency International where Nigeria is being listed as one of the most corrupt nations in the world. Folashade et al.(2023) and Adomi (2018) have concluded it, when he opined that cybercrime has created an image nightmare for Nigeria. He said that most scam e-mails are thought to originate from Nigeria or Nigerians which is not always the case. Nigerians are treated with suspicion in business dealings and transactions.

2. Lack of Trust and Confidence Hinders Profitable Transaction: Nigerians are not trusted when it comes to business transaction in most countries abroad, the major reason for this is the level of fraudulent activities committed in their country that have been attributed to Nigerian citizens, therefore foreign investors find it difficult to trust Nigerians because of the fear of losing their money and goods. In many cases, online transactions are made but the buyers never receive goods from sellers, this is why some online shopping sites refuse to include Nigeria on their list of countries for delivery e.g. eBay (Adomi, 2018).

3. Denied Opportunities for Nigerians Abroad: The situation of Nigeria's image is in direct comparison with the famous saying "One bad apple spoils the bunch" because majority of Nigerians who do not have the slightest idea of what it takes to be a fraudster are suffering under the bad reputation umbrella created by those Nigerians caught. Folashade et al. (2023), opined that cybercrime has negative consequences. Cybercrime threatens foreign investment as well as misrepresents the country among other nations as corrupt. It will also lead to stigmatization of business men and women and they will face certain barriers when carrying out legitimate businesses. Majority of the business men and women go through strenuous screening before foreigners would eventually agree to transact business with them.

4. Inimical to the Progress and Development in the Country: Foreign direct investment is one of the major forms of economic development for a country and the refusal of foreign companies to invest may cause a retarded growth, however significant in the economy of the home country. Fear of fraud is a major deterrence for foreign companies. The inevitable cycle of events if this continues, would result into “No Investment No Development, No Development No Employment and No Development and Employment No Progress”. The amount of business deals and investment prospects that have been lost by Nigeria as a country due to fraudulent speculations is enough to make a significant change in all federating states of Nigeria (Folashade, 2023).

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The proposed theoretical framework is containment theory. Containment theory was developed by Walter Reckless in 1961. This theory suggests that individuals are pushed and pulled into crime. Pushes are elements that pressure individuals to engage in delinquency while pulls draw individuals away from accepted forms of behavior. The theory states that pushes and pulls are buffered by inner and outer containment. The inner containment includes self-concept, goal orientation, frustration tolerance, and norm commitment and retention (i.e. elements within the individual’s self). The outer containment includes the social environment in which the individual resides and reflects socialization within the community (i.e. elements outside one’s self) (Onyejegbu et al., 2021).

Containment theory asserts that there is an ordering to these elements, with factors of inner containment being developed to address the onset of deviant pushes and factors of outer containment serving as secondary reinforcement mechanisms and buffers against deviant pulls. According to Reckless, we should expect to see factors of inner containment exhibit a strong and primary influence on decision making over the factors of outer containment (Ngozi et al., 2021). A situation that may push an individual towards a deviant act is one in which the individual feels some type of pressure to engage in order to escape or improve their current situation (Lilly et al, 2017 in Ngozi et al., 2021). As the individual is self-interested, the presence of the negative situation is pushing them toward a socially undesirable act because they see this act as a way to alleviate their current pain. The only thing keeping the individual from engaging in undesirable behaviour is the presence of strong factors of inner or outer containments (Ngozi et al., 2021).

In this context, most Nigerian millennials are pushed to cyber fraud by the failures of their imagined futures to come true as they had imagined. These failures make them seek alternatives to bring their dreams to reality and mostly resort to cyber fraud as a quick, but desperate means. The millennials are also pulled to cyber fraud by the lack of societal laws and systems that allow them to express their creativity and get rewarded for doing so. This is seen in how tight the leadership cults in Nigeria are, allowing only a handful of people into leadership positions and keeping the young and innovative millennials out of leadership systems. With the increasing popularity of Nigeria’s personality in cyber fraud, a new pull is created that affects the neo-economy and likely the future of Nigeria. This new pull builds a vicious cycle of cybercrime in Nigeria by targeting the foundation of modern economies in Nigeria.

EMPIRICAL REVIEW

Nogzi et al. (2021)- Despite the large scale provisions within the Nigerian legal framework that address the issue of cyber frauds, there is an alarming increase in cyber-offences in Nigeria. This necessitated the present study that employed semi-structured interviews to draw

data from civil servants from grade level twelve and above and business owners aged 40 years and over [N = 34]. The study participants were recruited through a purposive sampling method and data were analyzed thematically. Results show that individuals and different organizations are often hit through direct hacking, malware planting, and many other more sophisticated means by cyber-criminals.

Enaikele et al. (2022) investigated the factors that could have influenced the inordinate desire of these youths to get rich quick and accumulate sudden wealth and riches. The study was carried out in Oshogbo. Accidental sampling method was employed to sample a cross section of respondents from the indigenous communities in Oshogbo. Three hundred and sixty (360) respondents were randomly selected and sampled with open and close-ended questionnaires. Out of this figure, three hundred and forty one (341) questionnaires properly filled and returned were analysed for the study. An in-depth unstructured interview (IDI) was also conducted with five other respondents in each of the indigenous communities. The study reveals that the present inordinate desperation of the youths to get-rich-quick is influenced by unemployment, online and Nollywood videos, peer influence, poor parenting and change in societal value system, economic deprivation and inequality in wealth distribution characterized by marginalization, limited opportunities and social exclusion of these youths perpetrating the criminal acts.

Anthony and Onos (2022) studied on ethico-religious evaluation of 'yahoo-yahoo' fraud in Nigeria. This paper analyzed cybercrime (Yahoo Yahoo) from ethical and religious paradigms. The paper adopts the evaluative and descriptive methods of research. The findings show that several factors like poverty, unemployment, dwindling societal value and greed are responsible for the menace. The paper concludes that the act is not ethically and religiously justifiable. Furthermore, there is need to increase societal, religious and family values, such as sanctity of human life, dignity of labour, integrity, and contentment as a way forward.

Chukwuka (2022) investigated on internet fraud: the menace of 'yahoo boys' and the deceitfulness of riches. The paper discovered that greed, lack of job for the teaming youths, absence of financial regulation, government inability to adequately punish offenders among others are factors fuelling the yahoo business which remains a threat to national development. The paper recommended that the government should be more decisive in punishing those who are involved in cyber crime to serve as deterrent to others.

Nwokoro et al. (2022) investigates from the perceptions of youths on the incessant engagement of unscrupulous youths in cybercrime in Owerri Municipal in Imo state Nigeria, and the factors that predispose them to engage in this crime. The study posed three research questions, and adopted a mixed method approach, whereby 300 youths selected from Owerri municipal in Imo state were shared questionnaires to fill and submit, and another 10 youths interviewed. About 285 questionnaires were retrieved and used for the analysis. The findings showed that yahoo-yahoo is a type of cybercrime perpetrated with the aid of the internet and social media handles, of which the Facebook app is mostly used. The study equally showed that the perpetrators of this cybercrime target their victims through anchor social media such as Facebook, WhatsApp, Instagram and Tweeter, of which the Facebook was reportedly mostly used.

Asuai and Eбенуwa-Okoh (2023) investigated the relationship among religious beliefs, peer pressure and the get-rich-quick syndrome among Delta State University undergraduates. The study used the correlational method of ex-post facto research design. The target population of this study comprised the entire undergraduates of universities in Delta State in the 2020/2021

academic session, with a total population of 25,575 undergraduates. A sample size of 384 undergraduates constituted the samples for the study, through proportionate and stratified sampling techniques. The research questions were answered with the aid of Pearson's correlation coefficient of determination. The hypotheses were tested using regression statistics at a 0.05 level of significance. The findings of the study revealed that there is a significant relationship between religious beliefs and get-rich-quick syndrome among undergraduates of universities in Delta State; there is a significant relationship between parenting styles and get-rich-quick syndrome among undergraduates of universities in Delta State; that there is a significant relationship between peer pressure and get-rich-quick syndrome among undergraduates of universities in Delta State; that there is a significant relationship among religious beliefs, parenting styles, peer pressure and get-rich-quick syndrome among undergraduates of universities in Delta State; and that there is no significant moderating impact of sex on the relationship among religious beliefs, parenting styles, peer pressure and get-rich-quick syndrome among undergraduates of universities in Delta State.

3.0 METHODOLOGY

This is a cross-sectional survey design study, whereby the researcher employed the quantitative method, which involved the use of questionnaire as main instrument of data collection. The rationale is that the quantitative method approach would provide an appropriate means for gaining a descriptive insight into get-rich quick syndrome on the aspirations of secondary school students in Nigeria. While, the population of the study comprises two hundred and fourteen (294) registered private and public secondary school in Port Harcourt, while the accessible respondents for the study were students (Rivers State yellow page directory, 2014/2015). Two hundred (200) students were drawn as the sample size. In terms of the sampling method applied, the snowballing method was mainly used for selection of participants for this study. Because of the nature of the study which is rather very sensitive and complex in nature, the snow ball sampling method allowed the researcher to reach very hard-to-reach people in the society (Denzin & Lincoln, 2011). A total number of 200 copies of questionnaire were shared to secondary school students in Port Harcourt, however, only 164 were retrieved and used for analysis. In terms of data analysis, the study applied statistical, simple percentage, mean and standard deviation for analyzing derived questionnaire data.

4.0 DATA ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Two hundred (200) copies of questionnaire were distributed and some of the surveys were deemed useless and thus excluded from the study analysis due to observed blank or omitted items and inadequate questionnaire completing. One hundred and sixty four (164) copies were retrieved and useful, giving a response rate of 82.0% and thirty six (36) copies, representing 18.0%, was not retrieved.

Research Question One

Table 1: Mean (\bar{x}) and standard deviation (SD) on what are the activities of get-rich quick syndrome on the aspirations of secondary school students in Nigeria?

S/N	Items	SA (54)	A (43)	D (2)	SD (1)	Total	\bar{x}	SD	Remark
1	Cybercrime	74 33% 296	74 45% 222	12 7% 24	4 3% 4	164 100% 546	3.3	1.0	Agreed
2	Human rituals	76 42% 304	88 54% 264	0 0% 0	0 0% 0	164 100% 568	3.5	0.6	Agreed
3	Deceit	97 59% 388	67 41% 201	0 0% 0	0 0% 0	164 100% 589	3.6	0.5	Agreed
	Total	247	229	12	4	492	3.5	0.73	Agreed
		988	687	24	4	1703			

Source: Researcher's Field Survey, 2024

Table 1 gives specify appraisal on the activities of get-rich quick syndrome on the aspirations of secondary school students in Nigeria. The mean and standard deviation for each statement items were represented by Mean (\bar{x}) and standard deviation (SD) respectively. Evidence from the above table, indicated that the participated respondents agreed on each of the three (3) items as stated in the activities of get-rich quick syndrome on the aspirations of secondary school students in Nigeria (mean scores greater than 2.5 of the mean criterion $((4+3+2+1)/4)$). The grand mean score was equally greater than 2.5. It shows that students in secondary schools were aware of the activities of get-rich quick syndrome in Nigeria obtained a grand mean (\bar{x}) score of 3.5 and grand standard deviation (SD) score of 0.73. By this result, the activities of get-rich quick syndrome on the aspirations of secondary school students in Nigeria as indicated by their mean and standard deviation scores. These respondents' response results showed the activities of get-rich quick syndrome on the aspirations of secondary school students in Nigeria is significant.

Research Question Two

Table 2: Mean (\bar{x}) and standard deviation (SD) on what are the implications of students' involvement in cybercrime on the educational sector of Nigeria?

S/N	Items	SA (4)	A (3)	D (2)	SD (1)	Total	\bar{x}	SD	Remark
1	Tarnishing the country's education reputation	78 48% 312	68 41% 204	8 5% 16	10 6% 10	164 100% 542	3.3	1.1	Agreed
2	Denied opportunities for Nigerians abroad.	87 47% 348	72 44% 216	5 3% 10	0 0% 0	164 100% 574	3.5	0.7	Agreed
3	Lack of trust and confidence hinders profitable transaction.	81 49.4% 324	63 38% 189	16 10% 32	4 2% 4	164 100% 549	3.3	1.0	Agreed
	Total	246	203	29	14	492	3.4	0.93	Agreed
		984	609	58	14	1665			

Source: Researcher's Field Survey, 2024

Table 2 gives detailed evaluation on “the implications of students’ involvement in cybercrime on the educational sector of Nigeria? The mean and standard deviation for the statement items were represented by Mean (\bar{x}) and standard deviation (SD) respectively. Evidence from the above table, indicated that the participated respondents agreed on each of the three (3) items as stated in research question two (mean scores greater than 2.5 of the mean criterion (4+3+2+1)/4). The grand mean score was equally greater than 2.5. It shows that the implications of students involvement in get-rich quick syndrome through cybercrime has affect the educational system in Nigeria obtained a grand mean (\bar{x}) score of 3.4 and grand standard deviation (SD) score of 0.93. By this result, the implications of students’ involvement in cybercrime on the educational sector of Nigeria as indicated by their mean and standard deviation scores is in agreement with the respondents responses. These respondents’ response results showed that the implications of students’ involvement in cybercrime on the educational sector of Nigeria are significant.

Research Question 3

Table 3: Mean (\bar{x}) and standard deviation (SD) on “what are the causes of get-rich quick syndrome among secondary school students in Nigeria?”

S/N	Items	SA (4)	A (3)	D (2)	SD (1)	Total	\bar{x}	SD	Remark
1	Acute poverty influences cybercrime involvement among students.	81 49.4% 324	63 38% 189	16 10% 32	4 2% 4	164 100% 612	3.7	1.0	Agreed
2	Peer pressure is one the drivers of get-rich quick syndrome.	77 47% 308	82 50% 246	5 3% 10	0 0% 0	164 100% 564	3.4	0.7	Agreed
3	Acquisition and use of smart devices and accessories.	81 49% 324	63 38% 189	10 6% 20	10 6% 10	164 100% 606	3.7	1.1	Agreed
	Total	239	208	31	14	492	3.4	0.93	Agreed
		956	624	62	14	1656			

Source: Researcher’s Field Survey, 2024

Table 3 gives detailed evaluation on the causes of get-rich quick syndrome among secondary school students in Nigeria. Also, mean and standard deviation for the statement items were represented by Mean (\bar{x}) and standard deviation (SD) respectively. Evidence from the above table, indicated that the participated respondents agreed on each of the three (3) items as stated on the causes of get-rich quick syndrome among secondary school students in Nigeria(mean scores greater than 2.5 of the mean criterion (4+3+2+1)/4). The grand mean score was equally greater than 2.5. It shows that the causes of get-rich quick syndrome among secondary school students in Nigeria obtained a grand mean (\bar{x}) score of 3.4 and grand standard deviation (SD) score of 0.93. By this result, peer pressure, poverty and acquisition and use of smart devices and accessories has impacted on secondary school students engaging on various get-rich quick activities as indicated by their mean and standard deviation scores. These respondents’ response results showed the causes of get-rich quick syndrome among secondary school students in Nigeria to have significant.

4.1SUMMARY OF FINDINGS

The findings of this study are summarized below:

1. The responses on “the activities of get-rich quick syndrome on the aspirations of secondary school students in Nigeria” were all agreed by the participants.
2. Also, means scores and standard deviation score signifies that the statement items on research question two were all agreed by the participant.
3. It was also observed that, respondents agreed on the causes of get-rich quick syndrome among secondary school students in Nigeria.

4.2 DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

What are the Activities of Get-Rich Quick Syndrome on the Aspirations of Secondary School Students in Nigeria?

Discussion will focus on findings from questionnaire. Analysis of data using mean and standard deviation showed the activities of get-rich quick syndrome on the aspirations of secondary school students in Nigeria obtained mean (\bar{x}) score of 4.3 and standard deviation (SD) score of 0.73. The RQ1 focused on finding the activities of get-rich quick syndrome on the aspirations of secondary school students in Nigeria. It was found out all participants are aware of yahoo-yahoo crime, and most of the participants believed that the cybercrime called ‘yahoo-yahoo’ is very rampant in Nigeria. The various reasons for engaging in cyber rime attracted high number of responses from participants. Our findings supported the works of Ngozi et al. (2021), results show that individuals and different organizations are often hit through direct hacking, malware planting, and many other more sophisticated means by cyber-criminals. Enaikele et al. (2022) study reveals that the present inordinate desperation of the youths to get-rich-quick is influenced by unemployment, online and Nollywood videos, peer influence, poor parenting and change in societal value system, economic deprivation and inequality in wealth distribution characterized by marginalization, limited opportunities and social exclusion of these youths perpetrating the criminal acts. Anthony and Onos (2022) findings show that several factors like poverty, unemployment, dwindling societal value and greed are responsible for the menace.

What are the Implications of Students’ Involvement in Cybercrime on the Educational Sector of Nigeria?

Analysis of data using mean and standard deviation showed the implications of students’ involvement in cybercrime on the educational sector of Nigeria obtained mean (\bar{x}) score of 4.1 and standard deviation (SD) score of 0.93. By this result, the implications of students’ involvement in cybercrime on the educational sector of Nigeria has been affected the aspirations of secondary schools. The following authors were in line with this present study: Chukwuka (2022) paper discovers that greed, lack of job for the teaming youths, absence of financial regulation, government inability to adequately punish offenders among others are factors fuelling the yahoo business which remains a threat to national development. Nwokoro et al. (2022) findings showed that yahoo-yahoo is a type of cybercrime perpetrated with the aid of the internet and social media handles, of which the Facebook app is mostly used. The study equally showed that the perpetrators of this cybercrime target their victims through anchor social media such as Facebook, WhatsApp, Instagram and Tweeter, of which the Facebook was reportedly mostly used. Asuai and Ebinuwa-Okoh (2023) findings of the study revealed that there is a significant relationship between religious beliefs and get-rich-quick syndrome among undergraduates of universities in Delta State; there is a significant relationship between parenting styles and get-rich-quick syndrome among undergraduates of universities in Delta State; that there is a significant relationship between peer pressure and get-rich-quick syndrome among undergraduates of universities in Delta State; that there is a

significant relationship among religious beliefs, parenting styles, peer pressure and get-rich-quick syndrome among undergraduates of universities in Delta State; and that there is no significant moderating impact of sex on the relationship among religious beliefs, parenting styles, peer pressure and get-rich-quick syndrome among undergraduates of universities in Delta State.

What are the Causes of Get-Rich Quick Syndrome among Secondary School Students in Nigeria?

Analysis of data using mean and standard deviation showed the causes of get-rich quick syndrome among secondary school students in Nigeria obtained mean (\bar{x}) score of 4.0 and standard deviation (SD) score of 0.93. By this result, some factors cause get-rich quick syndrome in Nigeria which include poverty, greed, unemployment, peer pressure and so on. The following authors were in line with this present study: Adeniran (2023) assertion that peer pressure compels young people in Nigeria, where making money as a proof of manhood encourage unscrupulous youths to engage in this fraudulent internet crime (Tade, 2023). Another most common reason for youth's engagement in cybercrime is because they lack other means of livelihood or source of income generation. This pointed to the negligence of the country's government in addressing youth's unemployment. The National Bureau of Statistics (2017) showed that about 79% of Nigerian youths are unemployed as at 2017. As stated by some participants reflected this notion, they believed that unresponsiveness of government about youths' poor economic condition has pushed most youths into cybercrime. In support of this notion, Ninalowo (2023) argued that these youths unfortunately live in a society where values and ethics are changing very fast. In a society such as Nigeria with gross structural inequalities, high rate of indiscipline, weak sanctioning system and wide gap between the rich and the poor, there is a tendency for the deprived to reject and embrace illegal means of achieving prescribed goals such as been wealthy in young age. Moreover, the corruption that is looming over the affairs of our so-called leaders, politicians and technocrats in the country has further given the youths more impetus to engage in crime in order to bask in affluence as these corrupt leaders. Hence, the best solution amidst others identified in this study, is for government to focus on improving the living conditions of the youths in the country. This will go a long way in changing their dispositions to engaging in cybercrime.

5.0 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Based on the facts presented in the previous chapter, it was avowed that the results of the present study were consistent with the plethora of previous studies as evidenced in discussion of findings, whereby the effect of the get-rich quick syndrome on the aspirations of secondary school students in Nigeria was seen to contribute towards the menace happening in our society. Internet crimes have been with us for decades now but the introduction of information and communication technology has made it more sophisticated and widespread. Infotech presents a lot of advantages but the abuse of it has resulted in many computer crimes globally. In Nigeria, the failure of the government at all levels to provide for the citizenry has forced the youths down to secondary schools to invent a new culture in order to sustain themselves economically. There is also failure on the part of parents to cater for the needs of their children and wards as a result the youths are forced to query the morality which hitherto had been accepted as the norms. The frustration which the Nigerian youths, especially the boys are exposed to has led them into all manner of crimes.

There are many sympathizers of yahoo boys in Nigeria today. The yahoo boys are well respected by some members of the society and if any is involved in a case, he is likely to win because he is ready to spend money to ensure his release. Many landlords today prefer to rent

their houses to a yahoo person who is ready to pay double what others are willing to pay. In some universities, the yahoo boys are given special treatment by the staff of the universities because of financial gain. To the yahoo boys, they are only being smarter and wiser. This inordinate recognition of yahoo boys has resulted in some secondary school students referring to education as a scam. However, despite the failures of the society, the menace of yahoo boys cannot be allowed to continue unabated. The future of Nigeria is actually hanging in a balance as the youths who are the leaders of tomorrow have taken to anti social behavior as the way to go. No nation survives without a strong moral code in place. The study therefore concludes that get-rich quick syndrome affects the aspirations of secondary schools students. Based on the findings, the following recommendations were suggested:

- i. The study recommends that because of the high rate and incessancy of this crime in the country, there is immediate call for remedies. An important solution is for government to address the poor living condition of youths, as well as the high rate of poverty and unemployment facing youths in the country.
- ii. More cyber security management such as data encryption and careful management of personal information in the internet were also identified as a way of keeping fraudsters from gaining access to personal information of people.
- iii. Parents should be sensitized about the negative effects of social media on youths to make them more careful and sensitive about the upbringing of their young ones.
- iv. In addition, the Nigerian government and security agencies should employ high level of cyber security to monitor the activities of these cybercriminals in the country.
- v. All manner of criminal behaviour must be punished no matter where it is found. Selective prosecution and shielding of criminals who are connected to the corridors of power have heightened youths' involvement in computer crimes.
- vi. There should be a re-orientation of the youths by schools, government, communities and non-governmental organizations (NGOs) that money is not everything. Having money without self-development and discipline also lead to frustration.
- vii. Government at all levels, while admitting their failures towards the future of the youths should assemble the yahoo boys and find a way of changing their mindset from stealing with the internet to using the internet to advance the course of the nation.
- viii. Parents should improve their relationship with their adolescents and choose the right parenting style that will help the adolescents to abstain from indulgence in the get-rich-quick activities.
- ix. Religious bodies should intensify efforts to address the issue of the get-rich-quick syndrome and find ways of dissuading their adherence from practising such unholy activities.
- x. Guidance counsellors and significant others should guide the students properly on the choice of friends they make within and outside the school in order to avoid being misled by deviant friends the students should be mindful of the kinds of friends they associate with and always double-check what they learn from their friends with their family value system.
- xi. Generally, parents and members of the community should endeavor to teach and uphold morals, values and ethics. Also, there should be strict adherence to the faith believed in and practice in order to instill good morals in to them.
- xii. For government agencies, law enforcement agencies, intelligence agencies and security agencies to fight and curb internet fraud, there is need for them to understand both the technology and the individuals who engaged in this criminal act.

REFERENCES

- Abiola, J. (2023). The impact of the information and communication technology on internal control's prevention and detection of fraud. *Global Journal of Arts, Humanities and Development Studies (SGOJAHDS)*, 5(2), 133 – 147.
- Adedayo F. (2021). Did Elon Musk use human parts for money rituals? (In) Opinion Column, *Premium times*, Accessed and Retrived Online in April 2024. <https://www.thecable.ng/did-elonmusk-use-human-parts-for-money-rituals>.
- Adeniran, A.I. (2023). The Internet and emergence of yahoo-boys sub-culture in Nigeria. *International Journal of Cyber Criminology*, 2(2), 368–381.
- Adomi, E. E. (2018). Combating cybercrime in Nigeria. *The Electronic library*, 1(1), 716-725.
- Akah, P. E. & Uzoh, C. E. (2019). *Compulsive desire for material wealth and unwholesome*. Retrieved from <https://www.ijsshr.com/journal/index.php/IJSSHR/article/view/492/438>
- Anthony, A. U.& Onos, G. I. (2022). Ethico-religious evaluation of 'yahoo-yahoo' fraud in Nigeria. *Abraka Journal of Religion and Philosophy*, 2(1&2), 33-54
- Asuai, E., & Eбенуwa-Okoh, E. E. (2023). Religious beliefs, parenting styles and peer pressure as correlates of get-rich-quick syndrome among undergraduates of universities in Delta State, Nigeria. *European Journal of Alternative Education Studies*, 8(1), 224-240. DOI: 10.46827/ejae.v8i1.4813
- Button, M. & Cross, C. (2023). *Cyber frauds, scams and their victims*. Taylor & Francis.
- Choi, K., Choo, K., & Sung, Y. (2023). Demographic variables and risk factors in computer-crime: an empirical assessment. *Cluster Computing*, DOI 10.1007/s10586-015-0519-8
- Chukwuka, O. (2022). Internet fraud: The menace of "yahoo boys" and the deceitfulness of riches. *Saientia Global Journal of Arts, Humanities and Development Studies (SGOJAHDS)*, 5(2), 87 – 97.
- Enaikele, M.D., Adeleke, T.A. & Adeoye, R. A. (2022). Get-rich-quick syndrome and the incidence of human rituals among South-West Nigerian youths: A sociological analysis of associated factors. *Kampala International University Journal of Humanities*, 7(3), 101–112
- Eze-Michael, E. (2021). Internet Fraud and its Effect on Nigeria's Image in International Relation. *Covenant Journal of Business and Social Sciences (CJBSS)*, 12(1), 1-16. [Http://www.Journal.covenant.ed.ngunivesity](http://www.Journal.covenant.ed.ngunivesity)
- Faturoti, K. (2022). *Five reasons why people engage in yahoo yahoo*. <https://hustle.ng/reason-engage-yahoo-boys-internet-fraud-scam/> retrieved 11-01-2024
- Kamruzzaman, M., Washington, S., Baker, D., Brown, W., Giles-Corti, B., &Turrell, G. (2020). Built environment impacts on walking for transport in Brisbane, Australia. *Transportation*, 43(1), 53–77

- Melvin, A.O. & Ayotunde, T. (2020). Spirituality in cybercrime (“yahoo yahoo”) activities among youths in South West Nigeria. In *Youth culture and net culture: Online social practices* (pp. 357–376). IGI Global.
- Ndubueze, P. N. Igbo, E. U. M & Okoye, U. O. (2023). Cyber-crime victimization among internet-active Nigerians: An analysis of socio-demographic correlates. *International Journal of Criminal Justice Sciences*, 8(2), 225- 234.
- Ngozi, I.-A., Ifeyinwa, A. A., Oguejiofo, C. P. E., Omaliko, J. C.& Oluchukwu, S. N. (2021). Get rich syndrome: Examining the fight against cybercrime in Enugu State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Criminology and Sociology*, 10(6), 1390-1396
- Ninalowo, A. (2023). Musing Over Campus Violence, Crime Wave and Social Structural Stimulus. *Readings in Campus Violence*, 3(1), 38-55.
- Nwokoro, C. V., Chima, F. O., Ndom, D. A. & Iheonu, O. M. (2022). Youth’s engagement in cybercrime (yahoo-yahoo) in Owerri Municipal of Imo State Nigeria. *Journal of Education & Social Policy*, 9(4), 117-130. doi:10.30845/jesp.v9n4p13
- Obadare, E. (2022). *Ritual killings in Nigeria reflect mounting desperation for wealth and security amid creeping collapse of law and order*. Accessed and Retrieved Online April, 2024. <https://www.cfr.org/blog/ritual-killingsnigeria-reflect-mounting-desperation-forwealth-and-security-amid-creeping>
- Obiezu, K. (2021). Nigeria’s epidemic of Internet fraud. *The Guardian Nigeria* <http://www.TheGuardianNigeria.com>, 7 Nov; 2021.
- Odo, C. R. & Odo, A.I. (2020). The extent of involvement in cybercrime activities among students in tertiary institutions in Enugu State of Nigeria. *Global Journal of Computer Science and Technology*, 3(2), 1-15
- Ogunrin, O. B. (2018). *Factors in get rich quick syndrome of Nigerian youths (a case study of youths in Ado Ekiti)*. Unpublished M.Ed. Dissertation, Federal University Oye Ekiti, Ekiti State.
- Ogwezzy, M.C. (2021). Cybercrime and the proliferation of yahoo addicts in Nigeria. *AGORA. Int Journal of Jurid. Science*, 8(2), 30-44
- Ojekodum, U. A., & Eraye, M. C. (2022). Socio-economic lifestyles of the yahoo-boys: A study of perceptions of university students in Nigeria. *International Journal of Cyber Criminology*, 6(2), 1001-1013
- Okogba, E. (2018). Fe of Ritualists in Delta: We anoint our pants to escape yahoo boys- warri girls. *Vanguard*.
- Oladoye, A. O., & Ushie, M. A. (2019). Socio-cultural factors as determinants of childbirth intervals in Cross River State, Nigeria. *Journal Multi- Disciplinary Journal of Research and Development Perspective Volume*, 4(2)184-192.
- Onodarho, A. (2021). *Trumpet: Warning Guide for students of Tertiary Institutions in Nigeria. Nigeria: SECDRAT*
- Onyejegbu, D.C., Onwuama, E.M., Onah, C.I., Okpa, J.T., & Ajah, B.O. (2021). Special courts as Nigerian criminal justice response to the plight of awaiting trial inmates in

Ebonyi State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Criminology and Sociology*, 10(1), 1172-1177. <https://doi.org/10.6000/1929-4409.2021.10.136>

Regner, S., Jeimy, C., Victor, C. & Jordi, S. (2022). Cybercrime and cybercriminals: A comprehensive study. *International Journal of Computer Networks and Communications Security*, 4(6), 165–176.

Tade, O. (2023). A spiritual dimension to cybercrime in Nigeria: The ‘yahoo plus’ phenomenon. *Human Affairs*, 23(4), 689-705.

Templar, R. (2020). *The rules of wealth*. Pearson Education Limited

Ucha, C. (2020). Poverty in Nigeria: Some dimension and contributing factors. *Global Majoritye- Journal*, 1(1), 46-56.

World Bank (2020). *Nigeria releases new report on poverty and inequality in the country*. <https://www.worldbank.org/en/programs/lsm/brief/nigeria-releases-new-report-on-poverty-and-inequality-in-country>